

Logistics Management Practices and Organisational Sustainability of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria.

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Received 25 January, 2025, Accepted 10 February, 2025, Published 20 March 2025

The study investigated the link between Logistics Management Practices (dimensioned by green logistics and reverse logistics) and organisational sustainability (measured by environmental, economic and social sustainability) of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria. The research was grounded by the Moral Responsibility Theory of Corporate Sustainability and underpinned by the philosophical paradigm of positivism. The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey approach, with a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale. The target population was 194 maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria which are registered with the Nigerian Port Authority. However, the elements of the accessible population were restricted to 950 management staff drawn from the 98 maritime logistic companies located in Rivers, Delta and Cross River States with the presence of ports activities. The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was utilised to determine a sample size of 274 respondents, and the simple random sampling was adopted with the aid of random numbers. Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence that highlights the crucial role of Reverse Logistics in driving Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability in the maritime logistics sector. It also reveals that Green Logistics is significantly related with Economic Sustainability. However, Green Logistics, in its current implementation, does not have a significant nexus with environmental and social sustainability. Therefore, it was recommended that Managers of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should enhance the adoption of reverse logistics practices in order to improve environmental, economic and social sustainability. However, based on the finding that green logistics is not significantly related with environmental and social sustainability, therefore Managers of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should embrace requisite strategies of promoting sustainability, such as community engagement practices as well as diversity and inclusion.

Keywords: Logistics Management Practices, Green Logistics, Reverse Logistics, Organisational Sustainability,

INTRODUCTION

The maritime logistics industry is a major catalyst for socioeconomic development and has become one of the essential elements of trade as more than 90% of Nigeria's imports and export are by sea. Moreover, over 80% of the country's GDP is derived from maritime related businesses (Bashiru, Muse & Lawal-Fagbo, 2021;

Osadume & Okuoyibo, 2020). However, the sector is bedevilled by several challenges which include lack of intermodal transportation systems, delayed berthing of vessels, lack of space for empty containers, inflation, low level of infrastructural facilities and high turnaround time of vessels and trucks (Njoku, Yomi & Sunday, 2020; Omoke et al., 2019). The resultant effect of these challenges is weak level of organisational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria. As such, the importance of organisational sustainability

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cannot be overemphasised. Organisational sustainability increases the capacity of an organisation to survive and promotes the rational use of natural resources; Moreso, organisational sustainability contributes to the increase of competitiveness, control, and performance of the companies (Barbieri et al., 2010). Lung and Levrat (2014) argued that organisational sustainability reflects the development that meets up with the needs of present situation of the society and the organization without compromising the condition of future of the generation to come to achieve their own needs. This study adopts environmental sustainability, economic sustainability and social sustainability as the measures of organisational sustainability (Nicolăescu, Alpopi & Zaharia, 2015; Cella-De-Oliveira, 2013).

In this context, environmental sustainability refers to a condition of balance, resilience, and interconnectedness that allows human society to satisfy its needs while neither exceeding the capacity of its supporting ecosystems to continue to regenerate the services necessary to meet those needs nor by our actions diminishing biological diversity, while economic sustainability refers to the ability of a firm to ensure that economic activities can be maintained over time without compromising the well-being of future generations (Morelli, 2011). Relatedly, social sustainability encompasses notions of equity, empowerment, accessibility, participation, sharing, cultural identity, and institutional stability (Mak & Peacock, 2011). Furthermore, this study adopted logistics management practices (dimensioned by green logistics and reverse logistics) as a predictor of organisational sustainability of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem of weak level of organizational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria, has become very critical. Scholars (Bashiru, Muse & Lawal-Fagbo, 2021; Osadume & Okuoyibo, 2020) have argued that the rapid growth in container ship size has increased the pressure on container terminal operators, thus resulting to port congestion. The manifestation of weak level of organisational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria is reflected in the fact that these companies lack sufficient levels of environmental, economic and social sustainability (Igbodo, 2018).

These maritime logistic companies are not able to adequately analyze sustainability-related risks and chances with stakeholders, nor provide a mechanism for the prevention of pollution and contamination by environmentally hazardous substances, neither do they sufficiently monitor their current level of environmental and economic performance (Nicolaesal, Alpopi & Zacharia, 2015). On the other hand, insufficient social

sustainability practices is reflected by inability of the maritime logistic companies to offer sufficient safety conditions and occupational health, so as to minimize rates of accidents (such as the fire outbreak at Indorama Company's gate at Eleme, Rivers State), lesions, occupational illness, sick days, and deaths related to work. Besides, some of these firms do not show adequate concerns with the quality of life of its workers and the society (Opuware & Ambakederemo, 2018). The effects poor level of organisational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria, are reflected in road accidents and deaths resulting from broken down container-carrying trucks on the road, reduction of competitiveness and decline in the number of vessels calling at the ports. For instance, the indigenous Ship Owners Association of Nigeria (ISOAN) have argued that Nigeria loses roughly \$300 million every year due to capital flights perpetrated by foreign maritime operators in the Nigerian seaborne activities.

Furthermore, maritime logistic pundits have argued that the causes of poor organisational sustainability include lack of capital, poor incentives for investors, poor integrated transport system, inadequate equipment; dominance of foreign vessel, deficiency in exports, as well as inadequate shipping management skills, knowledge and experience (Ekpo, 2012). Several organizational sustainability strategies suggested by researchers include eco-efficiency (Savitz & Weber, 2007); management competences (Maggi, 2006); competitiveness (Biggemann, Williams & Kro, 2014); product differentiation (Chen & Uzelac, 2015), adequate regulations (Ross, 2017) and protection of the ecosystem (Obradovic-Wochnik & Dodds, 2015). Despite the plethora of literature that claim to provide plausible panaceas to the challenge of weak level organizational sustainability, the problem is still apparent among maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria. Thus, a contextual gap in literature is hereby identified. Therefore, this study sought to close the lacuna by critically examining logistics management practices and how it relates to organisational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria. The study aimed to achieve the following specific objectives:

- i. Assess the link between green logistics and environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the nexus between green logistics and economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate the relationship between green logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- iv. Determine the nexus between reverse logistics and environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- v. Ascertain the link between reverse logistics and

economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

vi. Assess the relationship between reverse logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

The research questions are as follows:

- I. How does green logistics relates with environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- II. What is the relationship between green logistics and economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- III. What is the relationship between green logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- IV. What is the relationship between reverse logistics and environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- V. What is the relationship between reverse logistics and economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- VI. What is the relationship between reverse logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?

The formulated null hypotheses are:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship green logistics and environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between green logistics and economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between green logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant link reverse logistics and environmental sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between reverse logistics and economic sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between reverse logistics and social sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of logistics management practices and organisational sustainability of maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria.

Source: Conceptualised by the Researcher. Dimensions of logistics management practices were adopted from various studies (Li & Kim, 2023; Mutie, 2021) while the measures of organisational sustainability were adopted from various studies (Nicolaesal, Alpopi & Zacharia, 2015; Cella-De-Oliveira, 2013).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics Management Practices: refer to the strategies, processes, and operations implemented by

organizations to ensure the efficient movement and storage of goods, services, and related information from the point of origin to the point of consumption. According to Christopher (2016), logistics management involves the

planning, execution, and control of the flow of goods, services, and information between the point of origin and the point of consumption in a manner that meets customer requirements.

Green Logistics: refers to the process of minimizing the environmental impact of logistics activities while maintaining operational efficiency. This includes adopting strategies such as using energy-efficient transportation methods, optimizing routes to reduce fuel consumption, and implementing reverse logistics to manage the return and recycling of goods (Dekker et al., 2012).

Reverse Logistics: refers to the process of moving goods from their final destination back to the manufacturer or supplier for the purpose of returns, recycling, refurbishing, or proper disposal. Reverse logistics plays a crucial role in enhancing sustainability efforts and optimizing resource use (Rogers & Tibben-Lembke, 2001).

Organisational Sustainability: refers to an organization's ability to manage its financial, social, and environmental responsibilities in a manner that ensures its long-term survival and success. Eccles, Ioannou, and Serafeim (2014) highlighted that sustainable organizations often adopt practices such as resource efficiency, waste reduction, and ethical labor practices.

Environmental Sustainability: refers to the responsible interaction with the environment to avoid the depletion or degradation of natural resources, ensuring that ecological systems can continue to function and support life for future generations. It involves adopting practices that reduce environmental harm and preserve biodiversity, natural resources, and ecosystems while supporting human needs (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002).

Economic Sustainability: involves maintaining and improving the economic systems over time, ensuring the responsible use of resources to meet current needs while securing future generations' ability to meet their own needs (Giddings et al., 2002). In the context of organizations, economic sustainability ensures that business operations are financially viable in the long run while being mindful of resource efficiency and environmental impacts (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002).

Social Sustainability: involves fostering a fair and just society by addressing issues such as human rights, labor conditions, community development, and equality. Social sustainability aims to create inclusive systems where all individuals can thrive, while maintaining a focus on cultural diversity, social justice, and the protection of vulnerable populations (Colantonio, 2009).

Theoretical Framework: The Moral Responsibility Theory of Corporate Sustainability underpinned this study. The theory which was developed by Ha-Brookshire (2015) postulates that for corporations to be truly sustainable, individual members of corporations must perceive corporate sustainability as a moral duty to which all others are ascribed in any circumstances and have clear goals/procedures in place to fulfill such duties. This

theory is particularly relevant to the present study, as it stresses the importance of engaging all stakeholders, including local communities and employees, by ensuring fair labour practices and promoting corporate accountability. Thus, the theory offers a framework for balancing economic goals with moral responsibility, which is crucial for the sustained success and ethical standing of these companies.

Empirical Reviews: Nwaulune, Ajike and Bamidele (2023) investigated the impact of green logistics practices on social sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. Survey research methodology was employed and a simple random sampling technique was adopted. A sample size of 519 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane methodology. The results showed that the social sustainability of a subset of FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, was significantly impacted by green logistics methods (Adj.R 2 = 0.066, F (5, 496) = 8.036, p < 0.05). Moreso, Okyere et al. (2023) studied the impact of reverse logistics on firm's survival in Kumasi. Exploratory design was employed and a total of 111 people were included in the sample size using snowball sampling. The data that was gathered was analysed using regression analysis. The findings reveal that re-manufacturing, reusing, recycling, repackaging, redistributing, reselling, and repairing and reconditioning are some of the main reverse logistics techniques used by these companies, and reverse logistics also contributes to the survival of organisations.

Likewise, Chukwu, Ihezue and Umeh (2024) explored the effect of logistics on the performance of transportation Firms in Enugu State Nigeria. 400 respondents in the sample were selected from a population of 1,052 employees. A systematic questionnaire was employed in the study to collect data. The findings of the study demonstrate that demand planning for logistics has a major impact on the safety delivery of transport companies in Enugu State (t-statistic; 6.445; P-value; 0.000 Sig-value; 0.05); likewise, storage and material handling have a major impact on the companies' ability to respond quickly (t-statistic; 11.226; P-value; 0.000 Sig-value; 0.05). To sum up, logistics is crucial in helping businesses achieve their goals of having more effective management systems.

Furthermore, Aopare, Anane and Sarfo (2024) studied the effects of reverse logistics on organizational performance of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in the Ashanti Region of Ghana. A cross-sectional survey was adopted and 30 senior managers of pharmaceutical manufacturing companies were selected. Both SPSS and Stata were utilised for data analysis, for Confirmatory Factor Analysis. The findings showed that reverse logistics is beneficial to performance (r=0.44, p=0.015) and is a key component of the majority of pharmaceutical manufacturing enterprises in Kumasi (83.3%). Wali

(2013) explored the information technology infrastructure and customer service delivery in the Nigeria commercial banks. The quasi-experimental study design was adopted. The researcher employed judgement sampling, sample method. There are forty consumers in the sample size, representing the eight banks. A questionnaire instrument was used as the data collection approach. The results showed that ITI compatibility and connectivity had a significant and favourable influence on customer service delivery reliability and accessibility. Similarly, Gacuru and Kabare (2015) examined the factors affecting efficiency in logistics performance of trading and distribution firms based in Jomo Kenyatta International Airport area, Kenya. The census approach was used. Thus, 42 managers from the study area's logistics service department were chosen.

The study discovered that the effectiveness of logistics performance in trade and distribution companies situated in the JKIA area is influenced by information technology, competency level, and business-to-business relationships.

Moreso, Okon and Ibanga (2022) examined the influence of sustainable logistics management practices on the operational performance of maritime logistics firms in Calabar, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, they selected 350 respondents from five major maritime logistics companies through stratified random sampling. Data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. Findings indicated that sustainable practices in inventory management, transportation, and waste management significantly improved operational performance metrics such as delivery time and customer satisfaction ($\text{Adj.R}^2 = 0.72$, $F(3, 346) = 15.321$, $p < 0.05$). The study emphasized that the adoption of green practices in logistics can enhance operational efficiency and reduce environmental impact in maritime logistics. Adebayo and Onwumere (2023) studied the effect of logistics information systems on organizational sustainability of port handling firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. Using a sample size of 275 logistics staff, they adopted a cross-sectional survey and analyzed data through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

The findings showed that logistics information systems positively influenced organizational sustainability by improving data accuracy, decision-making speed, and tracking capabilities ($\beta = 0.58$, $p < 0.01$). The study concluded that enhanced information technology in logistics directly supports the sustainability goals of port operations by improving transparency and resource efficiency. Also, Eze, Agbonna, and Chukwuemeka (2023) explored the impact of transportation management practices on environmental sustainability in shipping companies based in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A survey research design was utilized, with 300 respondents selected through simple random sampling. The data collected were analyzed using correlation and regression analysis. Results

indicated a significant positive relationship between eco-friendly transportation practices, such as fuel-efficient routing and low-emission vehicle usage, and environmental sustainability ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$). The study recommended that companies invest in eco-friendly transportation technologies to align with sustainability objectives and improve public perception.

Likewise, Udoh and Nwachukwu (2023) investigated the role of reverse logistics in enhancing organizational sustainability of logistics firms in Warri, Delta State. They adopted a purposive sampling technique with a sample of 200 logistics managers. The study used a mixed-method approach with regression analysis to interpret quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative responses. Findings revealed that reverse logistics practices, including recycling and reuse, significantly contribute to organizational sustainability by reducing waste and lowering operational costs ($\text{Adj.R}^2 = 0.54$, $p < 0.05$). Managers expressed that reverse logistics helps firms meet regulatory compliance and achieve cost savings, thus supporting sustainable growth in logistics operations.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey approach. This research design falls under the philosophical paradigm of positivism.

3.2 Population of the Study: The target population was 194 maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria which are registered with the Nigerian Port Authority. However, the elements of the accessible population were restricted to 950 management staff drawn from the 98 maritime logistic companies located in Rivers, Delta and Cross River States with the presence of ports activities.

Sample and Sampling Technique: The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was utilised to determine a sample size of 274 respondents, and the simple random sampling was adopted.

Method of Data Collection: This study adopted a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale.

Method of Data Analysis: Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

Decision Rule: This study relied on the Cronbach's Alpha 0.7 reliability threshold for all the constructs, as recommended by several scholars (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hair et al., 2014). Also, for a two tailed test, $t\text{-values} > 1.96$ and $p\text{-values} < 0.05$ are significant, while $t\text{-values} < 1.96$ and $p\text{-values} > 0.05$ are non-significant (Hair et al., 2014). Table 1 shows that 250 copies of the questionnaire were administered, 250 (91.24%) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, while 232 (86.67%) copies were found to be usable.

Table 1: Methodological Analysis of Response Rate

Items	Number /Percentage
Questionnaire Administered	274 (100%)
Returned questionnaire	250 (91.24%)
Properly completed and returned questionnaire	232 (86.67%)

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2024

Table 2 Gender of Respondents

		Gender		
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Male	145	62.2	62.2
	Female	87	37.8	37.8
	Total	232	100.0	100.0

Researcher's analysis 2024

Table 3 Age of Respondents

		Age of Respondents		
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	20 and below 29	42	18.3	18.3
	30 - 39	100	43.5	43.5
	40 - 49	60	25.2	25.2
	50 - 59	24	10.4	10.4
	60 and above	6	2.6	2.6
Total		232	100.0	100.0

Researcher's analysis 2023

Table 4: Educational qualification of respondents

		Educational Qualification		
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	WAEC/SSCE/NECO	24	10.4	10.4
	NCE/OND	24	10.4	10.4
	HND/BSc	140	60.9	60.9
	M.Sc./MBA	40	16.5	16.5
	PHD/DBA	4	1.7	1.7
Total		230	100.0	100.0

Researcher's analysis 2023

Gender Distribution of Respondents

The result from table 2, shows that where the frequency for the male, $n = 145$ (62.2%), the frequency for the female, $n = 87$ (37.8%). The results suggest a highly male dominant role in conflict resolution. The implications could follow several assumptions given the significance of the disparity in the gender distribution. One could pinpoint such disparity to possible inequalities existent in the societal systems which probably emphasize on certain role functions, or even possible patriarchal systems or cultures wherein males are afforded better opportunities rather than the female. Nevertheless, the evidence portends a germane need for bridging the gap of the gender disparity and places onus on the growing need for

equity for both gender groups through the availing of equality in empowerment opportunities.

Age Distribution of Respondents

Table 3 reveals that the result on the distribution for the age of the respondents demonstrates that a high proportion of the respondents are between the ages of 30-39 (100 respondents) with a high percentage of 43.5%, while the next group with high proportion of the respondents are between the ages of 40-49 (60 respondents), representing 25.2% of the respondents. However, the age group for a younger set (aged between 20 and 29) of respondents has a frequency of $n = 42$, followed by that of an older group of between 50-59, at n

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics (UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT PRACTICES							
GREEN LOGISTICS	232	17.53	4.732	.235	.244	-.076	.483
1) Our organization actively seeks to minimize carbon emissions and environmental impact in our logistics operations.	232	3.01	1.044	-.189	.171	-.120	.341
2) We prioritize the use of eco-friendly transportation modes (e.g., electric vehicles, bicycles) in our logistics activities.	232	2.99	.922	.183	.171	.218	.341
3) Our logistics practices incorporate sustainable packaging materials and waste reduction strategies.	232	3.09	1.082	-.165	.171	-.485	.341
4) We collaborate with suppliers and partners who share our commitment to green logistics principles.	232	3.09	1.127	-.081	.171	-.603	.341
5) Our organization regularly monitors and reports on key environmental performance indicators related to logistics.	232	2.96	1.112	.089	.171	-.678	.341
6) Green logistics initiatives are integrated into our overall corporate strategy and decision-making processes.	232	2.95	1.149	-.002	.171	-.760	.341
REVERSE LOGISTICS	232	20.21	4.832	.278	.244	-.217	.483
1. Our company offers product vendors, the product recall or packaging return or take-back service.	232	2.93	.992	.027	.171	-.496	.341
2. Our firm makes customers aware of product recall service provided by the company.	232	2.54	1.008	.334	.171	.052	.341
3. Our organization provides logistics service for reusable containers to product vendors.	232	3.82	1.181	-.701	.171	-.477	.341
4. Our firm returns used packaging and products to suppliers for recycling or reuse.	232	3.23	1.032	.014	.171	-.731	.341
5. Our firm offers special incentives to those who return packaging materials.	232	3.50	.953	-.174	.171	-.467	.341
6. Our company provides suitable guidance to clients on the environmental aspects of handling, usage, and disposal of the vendor's products.	232	3.05	1.031	.038	.171	-.405	.341
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	232	20.21	4.832	.278	.244	-.417	.483
1) Our organization makes public its environmental and social objectives.	232	3.04	1.235	.122	.244	-.947	.483
2) Our organization usually analyzes sustainability-related risks and chances with stakeholders.	232	3.24	1.167	-.017	.244	-.987	.483
3) Environmental sustainability is embedded in the corporate strategy of Our organization.	232	3.35	1.159	.138	.244	-1.158	.483

4) In our firm, there is a mechanism for the prevention of pollution and contamination by environmentally hazardous substances.	232	3.12	1.115	.255	.244	-.632	.483
5) In our company, environmentally hazardous substances management policy is clear.	232	3.05	1.078	.401	.244	-.712	.483
ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	232	17.53	4.732	.235	.244	-.076	.483
1) Our organization honours the taxes, tributes, fees, and other government contributions that enhances economic sustainability	232	3.01	1.044	-.189	.171	-.120	.341
2) Our organization does not practice disloyal competition, trust, monopoly or dumping on economic sustainability issues.	232	2.99	.922	.183	.171	.218	.341
3) Our organization's economic sustainability decisions are taken based on a formal strategic planning that encompasses the organization as a whole, made by professionals.	232	3.09	1.082	-.165	.171	-.485	.341
4) Our organization focused on risk management plans and evaluations, with concern of the company's capacity to honour financial commitment with collaborators and shareholders.	232	3.09	1.127	-.081	.171	-.603	.341
5) Our company has restructuring plans in case of exceptional events (economic market crash, natural phenomena, etc.).	232	2.96	1.112	.089	.171	-.678	.341
6) Our organisation is punctual in the payment of salaries, benefits, and contracts with suppliers and other partners.	232	2.95	1.149	-.002	.171	-.760	.341
SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	232	21.45	4.213	.287	.244	.367	.462
1. Our organization offers safety conditions and occupational health, minimizing rates of lesions, occupational illness, sick days, days off and deaths related to work.	232	2.84	1.152	.196	.171	-.588	.341
2. Our organization assists people with special needs, immigrants, minorities, etc.	232	2.91	1.025	.050	.171	-.252	.341
3. Our organization has a concern with the quality of life of its workers and the society.	232	2.54	1.008	.334	.171	.052	.341
4. Our organization communicates social policies to the society collaborators and disseminated through all hierarchical levels.	232	3.02	1.090	-.119	.171	-.820	.341
5. Our company offer free training and education to its workers and the society.	232	2.87	1.114	.180	.171	-.446	.341
6. Our organisation has a friendly relationship with the stakeholders, without exploiting them, aiming to create lasting partnerships.	232	2.84	1.152	.196	.171	-.588	.341
Valid N (listwise)	232						

Source: SPSS output of Research Data (2024)

Figure 2: Measurement (Outer) Model
 Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

=24; the lowest frequency occurs at the age group of 60 years and above with n = 6.

Educational qualification distribution of respondents

Table 4 revealed that the majority of the respondents which are 140 representing 60.9% are B.Sc./HND. holders, while 40 representing 16.5% are M.Sc./MBA holders. Interestingly, 24 respondents (10.4%) have WAEC/NECO certificates, while 4 respondents (1.7%) are holders of Ph.D. degree. The implication is that a large proportion of the respondents are well education and may possess higher levels of abstract thinking which would have enabled them to easily understand the and respond appropriately to the questionnaire. The majority of respondent still have post-secondary education and this reflect a deliberate effort by the stakeholders to gain education.

From table 5, the descriptive statistics for the study on Logistics Management Practices and Organizational Sustainability of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria indicate moderate levels of engagement

across the key variables. Green Logistics has a mean of 17.53 and a standard deviation of 4.732, suggesting a moderate level of implementation with some variability in responses. The skewness of 0.235 and kurtosis of -0.076 suggest a relatively normal distribution, with a slight positive skew, indicating that a few organizations might be more advanced in adopting green logistics practices. Reverse Logistics shows a higher mean of 20.21 and a standard deviation of 4.832, indicating stronger implementation and slightly more variation among organizations.

Furthermore, the skewness of 0.278 and kurtosis of -0.217 reflect a distribution that is nearly normal, but with a small positive skew. Similarly, **Environmental Sustainability** has a mean of 20.21 and a standard deviation of 4.832, reflecting moderate commitment levels, with a skewness of 0.278 and kurtosis of -0.417, indicating a slightly more flat distribution. Likewise, **Economic Sustainability** has a mean of 17.53 and a standard deviation of 4.732, reflecting moderate commitment levels, with a skewness of 0.235 and kurtosis of -0.076, indicating a slightly more flat

Table 6: Result for Reflective Measurement Models (CONVERGENT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY)

Constructs	Items	Convergent Validity			Internal Consistency Reliability			
		Path coefficient (β)	Indicator Reliability (β^2)	AVE	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)	Effect sizes (f^2)	Predictive Accuracy (R^2)	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
GREEN LOGISTICS	1) Our organization actively seeks to minimize carbon emissions and environmental impact in our logistics operations.	0.690	0.476	0.560	0.884	0.198	0.165	0.856
	2) We prioritize the use of eco-friendly transportation modes (e.g., electric vehicles, bicycles) in our logistics activities.	0.788	0.621					
	3) Our logistics practices incorporate sustainable packaging materials and waste reduction strategies.	0.823	0.677					
	4) We collaborate with suppliers and partners who share our commitment to green logistics principles.	0.770	0.593					
	5) Our organization regularly monitors and reports on key environmental performance indicators related to logistics.	0.695	0.483					
	6) Green logistics initiatives are integrated into our overall corporate strategy and decision-making processes.	0.713	0.508					
REVERSE LOGISTICS	1. Our company offers product vendors, the product recall or packaging return or take-back service.	0.763	0.582	0.642	0.914	0.063	0.059	0.896
	2. Our firm makes customers aware of product recall service provided by the company.	0.796	0.634					
	3. Our organization provides logistics service for reusable containers to product vendors.	0.777	0.604					
	4. Our firm returns used packaging and products to suppliers for recycling or reuse.	0.692	0.479					
	5. Our firm offers special incentives to those who return packaging materials.	0.848	0.719					
	6. Our company provides suitable guidance to clients on the environmental aspects of handling, usage, and disposal of the vendor's products.	0.914	0.835					
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	1) Our organization makes public its environmental and social objectives.	0.822	0.676	0.661	0.907	1.372	0.578	0.873
	2) Our organization usually analyzes sustainability-related risks and chances with stakeholders.	0.769	0.591					
	3) Environmental sustainability is embedded in the corporate strategy of Our organization.	0.792	0.627					
	4) In our firm, there is a mechanism for the prevention of pollution and contamination by environmentally hazardous substances.	0.815	0.664					
	5) In our company, environmentally hazardous substances management policy is clear.	0.864	0.746					

ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	1) Our organization honours the taxes, tributes, fees, and other government contributions that enhances economic sustainability	0.599	0.359	0.533	0.870	1.300	0.565	0.822
	2) Our organization does not practice disloyal competition, trust, monopoly or dumping on economic sustainability issues.	0.578	0.334					
	3) Our organization's economic sustainability decisions are taken based on a formal strategic planning that encompasses the organization as a whole, made by professionals.	0.855	0.731					
	4) Our organization focused on risk management plans and evaluations, with concern of the company's capacity to honour financial commitment with collaborators and shareholders.	0.785	0.616					
	5) Our company has restructuring plans in case of exceptional events (economic market crash, natural phenomena, etc.).	0.791	0.626					
	6) Our organisation is punctual in the payment of salaries, benefits, and contracts with suppliers and other partners.	0.730	0.533					
SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	1. Our organization offers safety conditions and occupational health, minimizing rates of lesions, occupational illness, sick days, days off and deaths related to work.	0.779	0.607	0.614	0.904	1.133	1.133	0.870
	2. Our organization assists people with special needs, immigrants, minorities, etc.	0.845	0.714					
	3. Our organization has a concern with the quality of life of its workers and the society.	0.850	0.723					
	4. Our organization communicates social policies to the society collaborators and disseminated through all hierarchical levels.	0.834	0.696					
	5. Our company offer free training and education to its workers and the society.	0.788	0.621					
	6. Our organisation has a friendly relationship with the stakeholders, without exploiting them, aiming to create lasting partnerships.	0.569	0.324					

Source: SmartPLS4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

distribution. **Social Sustainability** shows the highest mean (21.45) and a standard deviation of 4.213, reflecting a somewhat stronger focus on social initiatives. The skewness of 0.287 and kurtosis of 0.367 suggest a relatively normal distribution with a slight positive skew. Overall, the statistics indicate that while there is moderate adoption of sustainable logistics practices, there is some variation in how different organizations are implementing these strategies.

Figure 2, and table 6 reveals the reflective measurement model of logistics management practices (dimensioned by green logistics and reverse logistics) and how it relates with organisational sustainability (measured by environmental sustainability and social sustainability) of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria, with the following interpretation: Green Logistics: The path coefficients (β) for Green Logistics items range

from 0.690 to 0.823, indicating moderately strong relationships between these items and the Green Logistics construct. The indicator reliability (β^2) values, which range from 0.476 to 0.677, show moderate reliability for the items. The average variance extracted (AVE) is 0.560, meaning that 56% of the variance in Green Logistics is explained by its items, confirming good convergent validity. With a composite reliability (ρ_c) of 0.884, the construct shows strong

Table 7 DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

	Environmental Sustainability	Green Logistics	Reverse Logistics	Economic Sustianability	Social Sustianability
ENVIRONMENTAL_SUSTAINABILITY	0.846				
GREEN_LOGISTICS	0.656	0.748			
REVERSE_LOGISTICS	0.801	0.721	0.813		
ECONOMIC_SUSTAINABILITY	0.774	0.733	0.784	0.819	
SOCIAL_SUSTIANABILITY	0.742	0.731	0.783	0.638	0.877

Source: SmartPLS4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

Figure 3: Structural Model showing the beta values and p-values
Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

internal consistency, supported by a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.856. The effect size (f^2) of 0.198 indicates that Green Logistics has a small to moderate impact on Organisational

Sustainability, and the predictive accuracy (R^2) of 0.165 suggests that Green Logistics explains about 16.5% of the variance in Organisational Sustainability. Reverse Logistics: The path coefficients (β) for Reverse Logistics range from 0.692 to 0.914, reflecting strong relationships between the individual items and the Reverse Logistics construct. The indicator reliability (β^2) values range from 0.479 to 0.835, indicating moderate to high reliability. An AVE of 0.642 shows that 64.2% of the variance in Reverse Logistics is explained by its items, confirming strong convergent validity. The construct has a high composite reliability (ρ_c) of 0.914, which is further

supported by a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.896, demonstrating very strong internal consistency. However, the effect size (f^2) of 0.063 suggests that Reverse Logistics has a small effect on Organisational Sustainability, with a predictive accuracy (R^2) of 0.059, indicating that Reverse Logistics explains 5.9% of the variance in Organisational Sustainability. Environmental Sustainability: The path coefficients (β) for Environmental Sustainability items range from 0.769 to 0.864, demonstrating strong relationships between the items and the Environmental Sustainability construct. Indicator reliability (β^2) values, ranging from 0.591 to 0.746, show moderate to high reliability for the items. With an AVE of 0.661, 66.1% of the variance in Environmental Sustainability is explained by its items, confirming strong convergent validity. The composite reliability (ρ_c) of

Figure 4: Structural Model showing the beta values and t-values. Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Table 8 : Results of Hypotheses Testing

Null Hypo.	Stages	Path Coefficients (β)	R ²	T Statistics (t) ≥ 1.96	P Values (p) < 0.05	Decision on Null Hypotheses
H ₀₁	GRELOGS→ENVRUSUS	-0.010 (Weak)	0.236 Weak	0.115 (Not Significant)	0.909 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₂	GRELOGS→ECOSUS	0.462 (Moderate)	0.603 Moderate	8.852 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported
H ₀₃	GRELOGS→SOCSUS	0.121 (Weak)	0.303 Weak	1.743 (Not Significant)	0.081 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₄	REVLOGS→ENVRUSUS	0.604 (Weak)	0.610 Moderate	6.905 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported
H ₀₅	REVLOGS→ECOSUS	0.527 (Moderate)	0.688 Moderate	9.189 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported
H ₀₆	REVLOGS→SOCSUS	0.811 (Strong)	0.788 Strong	14.149 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported

Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

0.907 indicates excellent internal consistency, supported by a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.873. The large effect size (f²) of 1.372 shows that Environmental Sustainability has a significant impact on Organisational Sustainability, and

the R² value of 0.578 suggests that it explains 57.8% of the variance in Organisational Sustainability. For Economic Sustainability, the β values range from 0.578 to 0.855, indicating moderate to strong relationships. The

indicator reliability (β^2) values range from 0.334 to 0.731, indicating moderate to high reliability for the items. With an AVE of 0.533, 53.3% of the variance in Economic Sustainability is explained by its items, confirming good convergent validity. The construct has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.822. Social Sustainability: The β values for Social Sustainability range from 0.569 to 0.850, indicating moderate to strong relationships with the Social Sustainability construct. The β^2 values range from 0.324 to 0.723, indicating moderate to high reliability for the items. With an AVE of 0.614, 61.4% of the variance in Social Sustainability is explained by its items, confirming good convergent validity. The construct has a composite reliability (ρ_c) of 0.904, demonstrating strong internal consistency, which is further supported by a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.870.

As revealed in table 7, the discriminant validity demonstrates that the constructs in the study—Green Logistics, Reverse Logistics, Environmental Sustainability, Economic Sustainability and Social Sustainability—are distinct from each other, as indicated by the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The diagonal values, which represent the square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), are all greater than the off-diagonal correlations, confirming that each construct shares more variance with its own items than with other constructs. For example, Environmental Sustainability has a square root of AVE of 0.846, higher than its correlations with Green Logistics (0.656), Reverse Logistics (0.801), and Social Sustainability (0.742). Similarly, Green Logistics (0.748), Reverse Logistics (0.813), and Social Sustainability (0.877) each have higher diagonal values than their correlations with other constructs. This indicates that the constructs in the model are empirically distinct and measure different aspects of logistics management practices and organisational sustainability in maritime logistics companies, confirming adequate **discriminant validity**.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Green Logistics and Environmental Sustainability: From figures 3 and 4, and table 8, the results of the hypothesis (H_{01}) test revealed that there is weak negative and no significant relationship between Green Logistics and Environmental Sustainability of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria ($\beta = -0.010$; p -value = $0.909 > 0.05$; t -value = $0.115 < 1.96$; R^2 value = 0.236 , 23.6%).

Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected and the alternate hypothesis was not accepted. This is a surprise finding as it disagrees with Chukwu, Ihezue and Umeh (2024) who found that logistics is crucial in helping businesses achieve their goals of having more effective management systems. This implies that there is a low level of adoption

green logistics practices among Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria.

Relationship between Green Logistics and Economic Sustainability: From figures 3 and 4, and table 8, the results of the hypothesis (H_{02}) test revealed that there is moderate positive and significant relationship between Green Logistics and Economic Sustainability of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.462$; p -value = $0.000 < 0.05$; t -value = $8.852 > 1.96$; R^2 value = 0.603 , 60.3%). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This is not a surprise finding as it agrees with Chukwu, Ihezue and Umeh (2024) who found that logistics is crucial in helping businesses achieve their goals of having more effective management systems.

Relationship between Green Logistics and Social Sustainability: From figures 3 and 4, and table 8, the results of the hypothesis (H_{03}) test indicated a weak positive but no significant relationship between Green Logistics and Social Sustainability in Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.121$; p -value = $0.081 > 0.05$; t -value = $1.743 < 1.96$; R^2 value = 0.303 , 30.3%). Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting no significant relationship. The R^2 value of 0.303 shows that Green Logistics explains 30.3% of the variance in Social Sustainability. However, this finding is surprising as it disagrees with Nwaulune, Ajike and Bamidele (2023) who found that the social sustainability of a subset of FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, was significantly impacted by green logistics methods. This implies that the adoption of green logistics by operations of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria, is still at its budding stage.

Relationship between Reverse Logistics and Environmental Sustainability: From figures 3 and 4, and table 8, the results of the hypothesis (H_{04}) test revealed a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between Reverse Logistics and Environmental Sustainability in Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria (β value = 0.604 ; p -value = $0.000 < 0.05$; t -value = $5.588 > 1.96$; R^2 = 0.610 , 61.0%). This is not surprising as it agrees with earlier study by Aopare, Anane and Sarfo (2024) who found that reverse logistics is beneficial to performance and is a key component of the majority of pharmaceutical manufacturing enterprises in Kumasi.

Relationship between Reverse Logistics and Economic Sustainability: From figures 3 and 4, and table 8, the results of the hypothesis (H_{05}) test indicate a strong positive, and statistically significant relationship between Reverse Logistics and economic Sustainability of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria (β value = 0.527 ; p -value of $0.000 < 0.05$; t -value = $9.189 > 1.96$; R^2 = 0.688 , 68.8%). This finding is not surprising as it agrees with Okyere et al. (2023) who found that re-manufacturing, reusing, recycling, repackaging, redistributing, reselling, and repairing and

reconditioning are some of the main reverse logistics techniques used by companies, and reverse logistics also contributes to the survival of organisations.

Relationship between Reverse Logistics and Social Sustainability:: From figures 3 and 4, and table 4, the results of the hypothesis (H_{06}) test indicate a strong positive, and statistically significant relationship between Reverse Logistics and Social Sustainability in Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria (β value= 0.811; p-value =0.000<0.05; t-value =14.149>1.96; R^2 = 0.788, 78.8%. This finding is not surprising as it agrees with Okyere et al. (2023) who found that reverse logistics contributes to the survival of organisations.

5.0: Conclusion: The study concludes that Green Logistics does not have a significant relationship with either Environmental or Social Sustainability. However, Green Logistics have significant link with economic sustainability. Conversely, Reverse Logistics demonstrates a statistically significant relationship with all of Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability, indicating that practices in Reverse Logistics substantially contribute to the sustainability outcomes of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Based on the finding that green logistics is not significantly related with environmental sustainability, therefore Managers of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should embrace requisite strategies of promoting sustainability, such as reverse logistics and community engagement practices.**
- 2. Management of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should increase the adoption of green logistics practices as a means of improving economic sustainability, by incorporating sustainable packaging materials and waste reduction strategies.**
- 3. Based on the finding that green logistics is not significantly related with social sustainability, therefore, Management of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should deploy other strategies of ensuring social sustainability, such as diversity and inclusion.**
- 4. Managers of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should enhance the adoption of reverse logistics practices in order to improve environmental sustainability, by returning used packaging and products to suppliers for recycling or reuse.**
- 5. Management of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should boost the adoption of reverse logistics practices as a means of improving economic sustainability, by offering special incentives to those who return packaging materials.**
- 6. Management of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should enhance the practice of reverse logistics as a way of improving social sustainability by**

providing suitable guidance to clients on the environmental aspects of handling, usage, and disposal of the vendor's products.

5.2: Contribution to Knowledge: This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence that highlights the crucial role of Reverse Logistics in driving Environmental, Economic and Social Sustainability in the maritime logistics sector. It also reveals that Green Logistics is significantly related with Economic Sustainability. However, Green Logistics, in its current implementation, does not have a significant nexus with environmental and social sustainability, suggesting the need for further innovation in this area.

5.3: Suggestion for Further Research: Future research could focus on identifying specific factors or barriers that limit the effectiveness of Green Logistics in achieving Environmental and Social Sustainability outcomes. Additionally, longitudinal studies could be conducted to explore how the implementation of enhanced Green Logistics practices evolves over time and impacts sustainability in the maritime logistics sector. Further investigation into the moderating role of regulatory frameworks and industry standards on logistics management practices could also yield valuable insights.

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APPENDIX I

QUESTIONNAIRE

LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND ORGANISATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY OF MARITIME LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA.

Please objectively respond to the following questions. Kindly tick the box for demographics in Section (A) and the item questions in Section B, C and D (with any option from strongly agree to strongly disagree as displayed). Kindly respond to all questions, even if they appear repetitive, and please note that there are no right or wrong answers. All information given shall be treated confidentially.

SECTION A:

Respondent's Demographics

(1) Gender? (a) Male (b) Female

(2) Age bracket? (a) 20- 29 (b) 30 - 39 (c) 40 – 49 (d) 50 – 59 (e) 60 above

(4) Highest educational qualification (a) WAEC/SSS/NECO (d) NCE/OND HND/ BSC (h) /MBA (h) Ph.D/DB

Section B

Kindly, indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree that the statement reflects the situation in your organisation.

LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT PRACTICES						
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
GREEN LOGISTICS		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization actively seeks to minimize carbon emissions and environmental impact in our logistics operations.					
2	We prioritize the use of eco-friendly transportation modes (e.g., electric vehicles, bicycles) in our logistics activities.					
3	Our logistics practices incorporate sustainable packaging materials and waste reduction strategies.					
4	We collaborate with suppliers and partners who share our commitment to green logistics principles.					
5	Our organization regularly monitors and reports on key environmental performance indicators related to logistics.					
6	Green logistics initiatives are integrated into our overall corporate strategy and decision-making processes.					
<i>Source: (Harris & Talley,2023;Mutie, 2021)</i>						
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
REVERSE LOGISTICS		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our company offers product vendors, the product recall or packaging return or take-back service.					
2	Our firm makes customers aware of product recall service provided by the company.					
3	Our organization provides logistics service for reusable containers to product vendors.					
4	Our firm returns used packaging and products to suppliers for recycling or reuse.					
5	Our firm offers special incentives to those who return packaging materials.					
6	Our company provides suitable guidance to clients on the environmental aspects of handling, usage, and disposal of the vendor's products.					

Section C

ORGANISATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY

S/N	ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization makes public its environmental and social objectives.					
2	Our organization usually analyzes sustainability-related risks and chances with stakeholders.					
3	Environmental sustainability is embedded in the corporate strategy of Our organization.					
4	In our firm, there is a mechanism for the prevention of pollution and contamination by environmentally hazardous substances.					
5	In our company, environmentally hazardous substances management policy is clear.					
6	Our company has a programme for monitoring our current level of environmental performance.					

Source: (Nicolaesal, Alpopi & Zacharia, 2015)

S/N	ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization honours the taxes, tributes, fees, and other government contributions that enhances economic sustainability					
2	Our organization does not practice disloyal competition, trust, monopoly or dumping on economic sustainability issues.					
3	Our organization's economic sustainability decisions are taken based on a formal strategic planning that encompasses the organization as a whole, made by professionals.					
4	Our organization focused on risk management plans and evaluations, with concern of the company's capacity to honour financial commitment with collaborators and shareholders.					
5	Our company has restructuring plans in case of exceptional events (economic market crash, natural phenomena, etc.).					
6	Our organisation is punctual in the payment of salaries, benefits, and contracts with suppliers and other partners.					

S/N	SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization offers safety conditions and occupational health, minimizing rates of lesions, occupational illness, sick days, days off and deaths related to work.					
2	Our organization assists people with special needs, immigrants, minorities, etc.					
3	Our organization has a concern with the quality of life of its workers and the society.					
4	Our organization communicates social policies to the society collaborators and disseminated through all hierarchical levels.					
5	Our company offer free training and education to its workers and the society.					
6	Our organisation has a friendly relationship with the stakeholders, without exploiting them, aiming to create lasting partnerships.					

Source: (Cella-De-Oliveira, 2013)